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Afsana KAZİMOVA

Araştırmacı, Azerbaycan. afsana.kazimova44@gmail.com

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ORCID: [0000-0002-3857-5809](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3857-5809)

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THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH IN AZERBAIJAN: TEACHING LANGUAGE THROUGH CULTURE

Abstract

A language is a system of communication that consists of a set of sounds and written symbols that are used by the people of a particular country or region for talking or writing. Intercultural communicative competence is defined to be at the heart of foreign language education more than communicative competence nowadays. In the Soviet Union, the teaching of English as a foreign language was based on 'grammar-translation', also called 'the classical method'. This method focused on learning grammar rules, memorizing vocabulary in isolation, translating from English, the foreign language, into learners' first language (L1), and vice versa. After a while, intercultural communication started to be used when communication was not sufficient, as students needed to learn about the cultures of different countries. This study is expected to contribute to the discussions about cultural and intercultural analysis of ELT coursebooks used in middle schools in Azerbaijan. The study aims to find and discuss cultural and elements in ELT coursebooks used in middle schools in Azerbaijan.

In this study, content analysis will be used. After reading textbooks, all passages, exercises, stories will be analyzed. Then they will be analyzed and discussed. In the study, it was investigated which aspects of culture are presented in ELT textbooks and whether idioms and proverbs are taught through culture.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Culture, Cultural Elements, Intercultural Elements, Language.

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AZERBAJCAN'DA İNGİLİZCE'NİN ÖNEMİ: KÜLTÜR YOLUYLA DİL ÖĞRETİMİ

Özet

Dil, belirli bir ülke veya bölgedeki insanlar tarafından konuşmak veya yazmak için kullanılan bir dizi ses ve yazılı sembolden oluşan bir iletişim sistemidir. Kültürlerarası iletişimsel yeterlilik, günümüzde iletişimsel yeterlilikten çok yabancı dil eğitiminin merkezinde yer almaktadır. Sovyetler Birliği'nde İngilizcenin yabancı dil olarak öğretimi, "klasik yöntem" olarak da adlandırılan "dilbilgisi-çeviriye" dayanıyordu. Bu yöntem, dilbilgisi kurallarını öğrenmeye, kelime dağarcığını tek başına ezberlemeye, İngilizce'den, yabancı dilden öğrencilerin ana diline (L1) çevirmeye ve bunun tersine odaklanmaya sebep oldu. Bir süre sonra, öğrencilerin farklı ülkelerin kültürleri hakkında bilgi edinmeleri gerektiğinden iletişimin yeterli olmadığı zamanlarda, kültürlerarası iletişim kullanılmaya başlandı. Bu çalışmanın Azerbaycan'daki ortaokullarda kullanılan ELT ders kitaplarının kültürel ve kültürlerarası analizine ilişkin tartışmalara katkıda bulunması beklenmektedir.

Bu araştırmada içerik analizi kullanılacaktır. Ders kitaplarını okuduktan sonra tüm pasajlar, alıştırma, hikayeler analiz edilecektir. Daha sonra kritik edilecek ve tartışılacaktır. Çalışmada ELT ders kitaplarında kültürün hangi yönlerinin sunulduğu, deyim ve atasözlerinin kültür yoluyla öğretilip öğretilmediği araştırılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Azerbaycan, Kültür, Kültürel Unsurlar, Kültürlerarası Unsurlar, Dil.

1. Introduction

One of the most important elements of culture is language. Language creates both the "thought" that creates culture and the "expression" that brings that thought to life. Language regulates man and his relationship with society. For this reason, language teaching is very important in terms of cultural transfer.

The most basic source used by both students and teachers during the transfer of culture in foreign language teaching is textbooks. For this reason, textbooks should be purified from deficiencies and excesses as much as possible in terms of culture. There are prominent elements in the culture of a country. Failure to convey these elements is a deficiency. The transfer of unnecessary details is expressed as redundancy. For this, it is necessary to find answers to questions such as how, how much, and which cultural elements were transferred in the sources written for foreign language teaching, and to compare the books prepared for English as a foreign language with these books.

A language achieves a genuinely global status when it develops a special role that makes it recognized in every country. Today, it cannot be denied that English has become a global lingua franca with non-native speakers of the language outnumbering its native speakers. Since roughly only one out of every four users of English in the world is a native speaker of the language.

Being able to speak, read, and write in English is one of the key features in the modern world. It enhances several possibilities for non-native speakers. People who know English can travel all around the world without any problems in communication and have more opportunities for getting a better job.

Most of the interactions take place among non-native speakers of English. For those, English is a contact language between people who share neither a common native tongue nor a common culture, and for whom English is the chosen foreign language of communication.

Nowadays, everyone can communicate with people from all around the world by using English as a foreign language. Therefore, the English language as a lingua franca plays a sizable function in every non-native speaker's life. Each person has special reasons to learn English. It is utilized in all international activities, including communication, science, trade, aviation, entertainment, radio, and diplomacy. It shows how important English to follow events and developments in the world. English has turned out to be more commonly used language in Azerbaijan due to Eurovision, Baku 2015 European Games, and Baku 2017 Islamic Games last 6 years. A lot of tourists visited Azerbaijan, so it became a more commonly used foreign language. All these activities encouraged the students to learn the English language.

2. The Relationship Between Culture and Language.

Language and culture are inextricably linked with each other. Language is a part of a culture, and culture is a part of the language, the two are intricately interwoven so that one cannot separate the two without losing the significance of either language or culture.

Ritlyova (2009: 105) defines culture as customs, values, typical behavior, attitudes and the overall approach regarding the way of life reflected in movies, songs, fashion, literature, and numerous products of art, but also in everyday use of the particular language, e.g. recognized proverbs, common idiomatic expressions or phrases which are characteristic for certain members of society and which significantly differentiate these people according to their age, level and specific area of education, as well as their position in the society, etc.". It means that culture is an indispensable and crucial part of daily life communication.

Peterson and Coltrane (2003), state that it is important to be aware of culturally appropriate ways of addressing people, expressing gratitude, making requests and agreeing or disagreeing with someone and also intonation patterns and behavior are important facts since they might be different in the target language speech community than their speech community. It is impossible to communicate effectively in a foreign language without learning its culture.

Language teaching includes more than grammatical patterns and linguistic items. Students should grasp communicative competence to achieve language proficiency. Communicative competence is an individuals' ability to communicate with people of different social and cultural identities. To achieve such competence, students should learn shared cultural understanding and tolerance of people from different cultural backgrounds. When it comes to culture teaching in EFL context, Bada (2000, p.101) states that "Cultural literacy, or awareness, must be given a room in any language teaching syllabus not only for its broad contribution to bridging gaps between cultural differences and building an atmosphere of tolerance and confidence among societies, but also for its significance in communicating simple needs and expressing meaning in ideas between individuals."

Briefly, culture is a crucial component of language teaching and it is not possible to teach it without referring to the cultural content. To integrate culture in the language teaching process, teachers should have cultural awareness and reflect their knowledge to their classrooms.

Language and culture are closely linked to each other. For many years, it has been considered that culture is a significant and indispensable part of language teaching. However, every teacher has a different perspective and application of culture teaching (Bucholtz et. al., 2017).

Children and also young learners need to learn about their own culture, the culture of others and culture in general because the students will get to know other people and learn a new way of life. People

can learn how to interact with others, how to behave properly in a new society to appreciate and understand others' cultures (Srivastava & Goldberg, 2017).

Foreign language teaching has several components including grammatical competence, language proficiency, communicative competence, cultural knowledge, etc. For many years, the integration of culture into foreign language teaching has been a polemical issue all over the world. On the one hand, some educators think that teaching another culture may cause cultural corruption of the first culture or may have an assimilation threat for students (Rangriz & Harati, 2017). On the other hand, especially in recent years, many foreign language teachers aware of the importance of teaching the culture of the target language in the foreign language teaching process. First of all, in 6th grade's cultural elements have been searched. Book's authors are Farida Guseynova and Naila Bagirova.

Different countries' cultural elements are also mentioned, if we look at page 31 we can find information about Azerbaijan. Novruz is our national holiday, about national pastries, eggs, traditions are given on this page, but idioms, phrases, sayings are not taught through culture; grammar, and new words are taught.

About "Independence Day" there is the phrase "red-letter day" (important memorable, a happy day), this is taught in that text.

UNIT 2

FREE TIME

Do you know that...

- **national holiday** - an official holiday of the country;
- **major holiday** - a big holiday in the world;
- **popular holiday** - a widely celebrated holiday. People like it very much;
- **local holiday** - a holiday celebrated in some regions or places;
- **religious/movable holiday** - a holiday that moves every year; some religious holidays are movable holidays;
- **red-letter day** - 1) a holiday in red letters in the calendar; 2) a memorable, important, or happy day.

READING

2. Read the passages and say the meanings of the words and expressions in bold.

New Year's Day

New Year's Day is on January, 1st. People often gather at the place with their friends **to see the old year out** and welcome the new year. People say each other: - Happy New Year!
- The same to you!

Republic Day In Azerbaijan

On this day Azerbaijani people **decorate** the cities with the **national flag** of free and democratic Azerbaijan. Azerbaijan people enjoy the day in the streets. People raise the national flag in the capital of Baku. In the evening people watch wonderful fireworks in the sky.

Independence Day

We celebrate National Independence Day on October, 18th. Independence Day is a national holiday in Azerbaijan and it is not one of the official **non-working** days and points as a **red-letter holiday**. You can watch concerts, see different historical films on TV.

Novruz Holiday

All our nation all over the world celebrate this holiday in spring. People like it very much. We do house cleaning, plant trees, make new dresses, dye eggs, **bake national pastries**, such as pakhlava, shekerbura and goghal.

Figure 1: English Textbook Unit 2, Page 32.

Solidarity day of the world Azerbaijanis, Ramadan, Sacrifice Holiday, Pomegranate Holiday is taught on page 32. First of all, students should know about their holidays, special days, about their meanings and it is good that this important information is given.

UNIT 2

FREE TIME

December, 31st - Solidarity Day of the world Azerbaijanis!

The Day of Solidarity means the **progress and national unity** of the Azerbaijani people all over the world. All Azerbaijanis of the world celebrate this holiday every year.

Ramadan (Eid Al-Fitr)*

Ramadan is the holiday of all Muslims in the world. All Muslims **fast** from sunset til sundown. They don't eat and drink during the daylight hours. They open their fasting after sunset. People spend hours **praying in the mosques**, visit old people and help poor families. Ramadan lasts a month.

Sacrifice Holiday (Eid Al-Adha)*

The Muslim world's second holiday is Eid-Al-Adha (Sacrifice). The day begins with morning **prayers**. The celebrations continue with visits to friends and family, give gifts to each other. People **sacrifice** an animal and share meat with the poor. They do charity work, Eid-Al- Adha lasts 3 days.

Pomegranate Holiday

It is a new holiday. People of Goychay region in Azerbaijan celebrate this holiday on the 4th of November. This region is famous for its best **pomegranates** in the country. It is a very interesting holiday. They make different **tasty things** from pomegranates.

3. Answer the questions and discuss.

1. Which holidays are the most important?
2. What is Solidarity Day holiday?
3. Why do you decorate your houses on holidays?
4. What do we do on Ramadan and Sacrifice holidays?
5. What other national holidays do you know?

4. Say which is ...

- | | |
|---------------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1. a moveable holiday ... | 4. a national holiday ... |
| 2. a major holiday ... | 5. a religious holiday ... |
| 3. a local holiday ... | 6. a red letter holiday ... |

***Ramadan Holiday** [ræmə ' dɑ:n] The ninth month of the year in the Islamic calendar

***Sacrifice Holiday** [sækrɪ ' faɪs] Religious holiday of Muslims, also called Eid al-Adha

Figure 2: English Textbook Unit 2, Page 35.

The degrees of adjectives are taught through these holidays and special days.

On page 35 there are texts about holidays, parties in Great Britain. There are some expressions and idioms in these texts. These expressions and idioms are taught, but the meaning of the expressions is not given.

Students can get more information about London, common and proper nouns and adjectives are taught through these texts.

Pronunciation is taught through teaching countries, in this page mainly the information is given about Azerbaijan.

UNIT 2

FREE TIME

READING

3. Read and give the meanings of the words and expressions.

In Great Britain children like to celebrate a Teddy Bear birthday party and a football birthday party. They make lovely things for these parties. They make a cake in the shape of a ball, a bear and a ship. Children **make a lot of things**: fancy dresses, party masks, party hats, name badges, invitations, and posters. Most children like to celebrate birthday parties and Christmas parties.

September, 9th is Teddy Bear Day. Teddy Bear Day is not **an official holiday**. In 1883 a German woman invented Teddy Bear [tedi beə] as a toy animal. Her name was Margarete Steiff. She was polio* and used **a wheel chair**. She had **innovative mind**. She **sewed clothes** in animals shape. Her little animals were popular and she made more toys. One of them was a bear. It was her hobby to make animal toys. These toys were elephants, pigs, dogs and cats.

Halloween is on the 31st of October. Children **dress in the costumes** of witches, ghosts, skeletons. Children go in costumes from house to house, asking for treats such as candy or sometimes money, apples with the question: "Trick or treat?" and give them to poor people. They **carve pumpkins** and put candles into them, light bonfires, tell scary stories each other and watch horror films.

On **Balloon party** children make different colourful decorations. Children like **to blow up** a lot of balloons, decorate them and put them in the corner, on the ceiling and at the doorway. There are a lot of interesting games in this party.

4. Match the halves.

- | | |
|------------------------------|----------------------------|
| 1. September, 9th is ... | a) in animals' shapes. |
| 2. A German woman was ... | b) Teddy Bear Day. |
| 3. She couldn't walk and ... | c) to make toys of animals |
| 4. She sewed clothes ... | d) Margarete Steiff. |
| 5. It was her hobby... | e) used a wheel chair. |

***polio** [ˈpɒliː.ə] it is an infectious disease

Figure 3: English Textbook Unit 2, Page 69.

In the unit "Countries and People", information is given about Italy, Brazil and Japan. The music, food and sports of these countries are given in the texts. Explaining lexical traditions, sharing ideas, developing speaking skills are discussed in this unit. Greetings, national holidays are also explained in this unit.

To learn our flag, emblem, symbols of flag, territory, population are important factors. That is why all this information is given on page 69 and all of them are also shown with pictures. Countries' flags are also given, but there are only a few questions about the passage.

UNIT 5

COUNTRIES AND PEOPLE

PRONUNCIATION

5. Pronounce the names of the countries with appropriate stress.

AMERICA [ə 'mɛrɪkə]

GERman ['dʒɜ:mən]

FrANCE [frɑ:ns]

BraZIL [brə'zɪl]

Great BRITAIN [gret 'brɪtən]

JaPAN [dʒə'pæn]

CHIna ['tʃaɪnə]

INdia ['ɪndiə]

CANAda ['kænədə]

AUSTRALIA [ə'streɪliə]

ITAlly ['ɪtəli]

EGYpt ['i dʒɪpt]

EngLAND ['ɪŋg 'lənd]

WRITING

6. Make up a story describing pictures.

Azerbaijan is my country. We have (D) ... flag and national (C)The emblem of Azerbaijan is (I)... . One of the symbols of Azerbaijan is a (H) There are more than (G) ... people in Azerbaijan. The territory is (E) Baku is the (A) ... of Azerbaijan. There are many (B) ... in Azerbaijan. They are Guba, ... , ... , ... , ... , etc. Our official language is (F).

- 9 000 000 - nine million
- 86 600 km² - eighty six thousand and six hundred square kilometers.

Self-Evaluation questions

1. What countries do you know in the world?
2. What symbols does your country have?
3. What is the meaning of our emblem?

Figure 4: English Textbook Unit 5, Page 70.

On page 70 there are some interesting listening and speaking activities for students. Even “What are countries famous for?” relates to the subject. Different pictures are given and students try to find out which country is famous.

UNIT 5

COUNTRIES AND PEOPLE

LESSON 2. THERE IS A COUNTRY

You are going to:

- learn different cultures
- describe world traditions
- share ideas developing speaking skills

WHAT ARE THE COUNTRIES FAMOUS FOR?

LISTENING-SPEAKING

1. What do you know about the countries?
2. What are countries famous for?

Word box

to be popular, kimono, to be famous, for complex, team, band, through, island, souvenir

1. Look and say what country is famous for.

Rice

- Italy
- Japan
- Brazil
- Egypt
- England
- Russia
- Turkey
- China

READING

2. Read and add your own opinions.

Egypt* is in Africa. It is an ancient country. All year round it is hot in Egypt. There are a lot of deserts in Egypt. People usually ride camels through deserts. Tourists visit Egypt to see the pyramids. This country is famous for the Pyramid of Giza Complex* and the Great Sphinx.*

Egypt [i:dzɪpt] - an Arabian country

Pyramid of Giza Complex - the oldest and largest of the three pyramids in Egypt

Great Sphinx [sfɪŋks] - a mythical body of a lion and a human head

Figure 5: English Textbook Unit 5, Page 76.

On page 76 there are two texts about “Carnival” and “Chinese Lantern Festival” and “Happy Holidays”. Students learn about carnivals, festivals, traditions, etc. They get information about. Then, various exercises related to the texts are done. It is an important activity in terms of getting to know cultural elements.

UNIT 5

COUNTRIES AND PEOPLE

6. Read and say the meanings of the words and expressions.**Carnival**

Carnival is the most popular **national holiday** in Brazil. Brazilian people celebrate it in February. All people go to the **musical parades** in Rio De Janeiro. They wear costumes and colourful masks, dance to the beats of drums and music. Carnival means «no meat». This is a tradition not to have meat on some days. This means **to keep away** bad things from their life.

Chinese Lantern* Festival

During this **spring festival**, people visit each other. They give different gifts on this day. People have fun on this festival.

Children go out into streets with **paper lanterns** and guess riddles on the lanterns. Lanterns are often in the shape of animals. People watch lions or dragons dancing. A typical food is **tangyuan***. They make it from rice balls with **sweet fillings**.

Happy Diwali

Indian people celebrate Diwali, the festival of lights. This festival is 7000 years old. Before the holiday people clean and **paint their houses**.

They wear new clothes. At night people light special small lamps and candles and put them around the home and garden.

They believe that **bad spirits** that walk around the house are afraid of the light. People also give special sweet to their friends.

Tangyuan [tāng yuán] - Chinese food

Figure 6: English Textbook Unit 5, Page 75.

Everyday expressions, traditions of British people, their behavior rules are taught on page 78.

UNIT 5

COUNTRIES AND PEOPLE

LESSON 4. BRITISH WAY OF LIFE

You are going to:

- make up dialogues
- speak about behaviour rules
- discuss traditions in your country

HOW DO ENGLISH PEOPLE FOLLOW THEIR TRADITIONS?**LISTENING-SPEAKING**

1. How do English people behave in public?
2. Why is it important to follow traditions?

1. Make up your own dialogue using the expressions.

- A:** Can I have tea?
B: How would you like your tea, with milk or sugar?
A: With milk, please!

Everyday expressions

With great pleasure!/ I am so sorry!/ Don't worry!

2. Read and put questions.

«**Excuse me**». If someone stands on your way, he says «Excuse me» and they will move out of your way.

Say «Sorry!». If you do something wrong say 'sorry'.

Don't ask lady her age. It is rude to ask about her age.

Cover your mouth. When yawning or coughing they always cover their mouth with a hand.

Don't greet people with a kiss. People do not greet each other with a kiss. They only kiss people who are close friends and relatives.

«**Please**» and «**Thank you**». It is a good manner to say «please» and «thank you». It is impolite if you don't do it.

Smile. A smiling face is a welcoming face.

Shake hands. When you greet someone, shake your right hands.

Don't pick up your nose in public. They use a handkerchief to pick nose.

Don't stare: It is impolite to stare at anyone in public.

Word box

to be polite, to stare, to behave, to shake, manner, public, to be proud of, strong

- A:** Oops! I am so sorry. I didn't see you.
B: That's OK! Don't worry! Can you help me?
A: With great pleasure!

Figure 7: English Textbook Unit 5.

Nouns, adjectives, and verb phrases are taught with the helping of short texts. What do they eat, drink, what type of foods do they have, which cards do they use, and for what, how the houses look like are mentioned. If we look through all passages, exercises, we notice that expressions, nouns, adjectives, phrases are mentioned, but there are no idioms, proverbs in this unit.

As far as I researched the 6th-grade textbook, there are several cultural elements, passages about different cultures. It is important and good that Azerbaijan's culture, traditions are given as the main factor. Students first should know about their own culture, traditions, behavior rules, because everybody always represents their country with everything. Then, several countries' cultures, traditions, manners are mentioned. The British way of life, cultures of London, Italy, Japan, Brazil, Chinese festivals are given. Their meals, music, sports are given.

In this book, we have researched that, students can get information about different countries, language is taught through culture, actually I can't find the answer to my most questions, but cultural elements are given.

The second textbook was written by Giztamam Guliyeva and Khalida Rustamova. In this book, we can find several cultural elements but there are not so many proverbs, idioms, phrases.

If we look at page 47, we can find some facts about countries. Texts are about serving tea in different countries. What countries love tea, how do they serve, what country prefers green tea, etc.

3 CW. Listen to the Fact File and answer the questions.

Fact File

The British, the Chinese, the Indians, the Japanese love drinking tea. The British first introduced tea into India. India is the world's largest tea-drinking country. The history of tea in China is old. They drink tea instead of water.

In the late twelfth century tea came to Japan from China. Tea is an important part of Japanese food culture. There are various types of tea in Japan. Green tea is also the central element of the tea ceremony. Tea has affected the history and economy of the world like no other **beverages/drinks**.

The British love tea with or without sugar. They drink several cups of strong, refreshing tea every day. This tradition started over 350 years ago. The five o'clock tea and tea with milk are among the greatest contributions of the British to tea culture.

1. What country is famous for its tea?
2. What is tea useful for?
3. What kinds of tea do you know?
4. In what country do people prefer green tea?
5. How do our people serve tea?
6. How do people serve tea in Japan/India/England?

4 PW/GW. Find True/False sentences.

1. The history of tea in Britain is long.
2. The English drink tea instead of water.
3. India is the world's largest tea-drinking country.
4. Tea is an important part of Chinese food culture.
5. Tea is an important part of Japanese food culture.
6. Green tea is also the central element of the tea ceremony in Azerbaijan

Figure 8: English Textbook Unit 5, Page 47.

I am trying to find out proverbs, phrases, idioms in all passages. Different countries' cultures are given, some grammar exercises, phrases, expressions are taught through culture, but it is difficult to

find proverbs, idioms, sayings in passages that cultural elements are given. It can be better if students learn also proverbs, idioms, sayings through culture.

“Health is Wealth” in this unit Azerbaijan’s traditional Novruz holiday, people’s hospitality is put forward more. I think, both our national holiday and hospitality teach students our culture, how people should behave to one another, what does Novruz holiday means, etc.

Vocabulary are given but there are not any exercises about phrases, idioms.

There is a topic about “Birthday traditions”. How do people celebrate birthdays in Denmark, Argentina, India, Netherland is mentioned.

In my opinion, birthday congratulations, phrases should be given, but there are not any exercises about them.

Lesson 3. Birthday Traditions

Getting ready for the task:

- What is birthday for you?
- What birthday traditions do you know?

Key words:

to hang - to attach smth

honour - great respect for smth/ to show great respect

to encourage - to give smb support

to survive - continue to live or exist

waltz - a dance performed by a couple

1 IW. Look at the pictures and talk about them.

2 IW. Look through the postcard and try to make your own.

Dear friend!
Please come to my
Birthday Party! On 21 May
at 6. At Nizami Street 12.
From Tunar.

Come to my Birthday Party!
We're honoured to see you
among us! It's my pleasure
to have you there!

Figure 9: English Textbook Unit 5, Page 65.

On page 65, we can find customs in different countries on New Year's Day. What do people eat on New Year's day, what are the meanings of these customs are given. There is a research exercise that, students should research by themselves, they should write facts on "How we celebrate New Year in our country"

3 GW. Read about the customs and find out what special food people eat on New Year's Day for good luck.

On New Year's Day in Japan people eat mochi-rice cakes for strength in the new year.

Some Americans from southern states eat black eyed peas and rice with collard greens. The black eyed peas are like coins and the greens are like dollars.

In Spain and some Latin American countries, people eat 12 grapes at midnight on New Year's Eve - one grape for good luck in each month of the new year.

It is a Jewish custom to eat apples with honey for a sweet new year.

4 IW. Read and correct the sentences on task 3.

1. The Japanese eat sweets for strength in the new year.
2. Some Americans eat black eyed peas. Black eyed peas are like dollars.
3. In Europe people eat 12 grapes for good luck in the new year.
4. Some Jewish people eat apples with candy for a sweet new year.
5. People in Latin America like to eat apples.

5 CW. CW. Sing the song "Jingle Bells" and sing together.

Figure 10: English Textbook Unit 6, Page 90.

Are flowers included in culture?

Every country has its national flower that has special meaning. Most flowers have a symbolic meaning, often one with a history of use that stretches back over the years. Various cultures around the

world have employed flowers and blossoms for different uses in their societies including religious rituals, wedding ceremonies, simple decorations, or any special meaning.

On page 90 and 91 different flowers are given. It was mentioned what countries the flowers belong to and what country they symbolize. Khari Bulbul, which grows in Azerbaijan, Tulip is a symbol of Holland, Red poppy is the national flower of Albania, Lotus is the national flower of India, etc.

3 GW/PW. Read the Fact File and search for more symbols of countries.

Fact File

Red poppy is the national flower of Albania.

Lotus is the national flower of India.

Jasmine is the national flower of Pakistan.

Calanit is the national flower of Israel.

4 CA. Look and match the pictures to the facts.

- A) is a symbol of England.
B) is the symbol of Scotland.
C) is the symbol of Wales.
D) is the symbol of Northern Ireland.

5 PW. Listen and complete the dialogue giving comments. Act it out.

Aysel: Samir, darling, don't you think to make a flowerbed in the corner!

Samir: We have far too many flowerbeds. What is a garden for, if it isn't for planting fruit trees, vegetables and useful things like that?

Aysel: Oh Samir, you know that a garden is a place for flowers.

Samir: Rubbish! I think of digging up the roses and planting a few cabbages or some onions and potatoes there.

Aysel: You'll plant them in my flowerbeds?! I have never heard of anything like that ...

6 PW. Make up a conversation answering the questions.

1. What is your favourite flower? Why?
2. Do you like to give flowers to your teacher/mother/sister/granny/ anyone?

Figure 11: English Textbook Page 110-111.

In every culture in the world, art has a great role.

Music plays an important role in culture, as we know countries' have musical instruments. Azerbaijan's national instruments are mentioned on page 110,111. First of all, students should know about their national musical instruments, their music, composers, then about different countries.

UNIT 8

ART AND CREATIVITY

Lesson 1. Music is Food for Our Souls

Getting ready for the task:

- What is music for you?
- What impressions can music create in you?
- What kind of music do you like to listen to and why?
- What can music give people?

Key words:

spiritual - relating to people's thoughts**appeal** - the quality of being interesting and attractive**to maintain** - to make smth continue at the same level/standard to keep**aesthetic** - made in an artistic way**mankind** - all human beings thought about as a large group**to enrich** - to improve or enhance the quality or value of smth

- 1 **CW/PW.** Listen to the passage and share your comments on music using the given words/word combinations.

high spirit, mood, entertainment, fun, useful, the part of life, enjoyable, a great pleasure, brilliant, important part, spiritual

Figure 12: English Textbook Page 114.

On page 114, a famous French singer, great Azerbaijani singer, famous composer, mugham singer, American singers are given.

Everybody knows that dance has an important role in every culture. Every nation's dances express different meanings. On page 117, different countries' dances are given, Azerbaijan's also is included. Dance is also part of the culture. It shows characteristic features, feelings of every nation.

2 GW. Listen to the passages and match them with the pictures.

a) "Flamenco" is a style of entertainment with lively song, music and **artistic** dance. It is very popular in Spain. A man and a woman dance Flamenco in **genuine*** Spanish costumes.

b) Everybody knows that dance has an important role in the everyday life of African people. They express their feelings of joy, happiness, sorrow or grief in their dances. Some African dances are very dramatic, some are very energetic.

c) Dance has always played an important role in the life of Greeks. They perform dances for entertainment, at weddings or harvest festivals. They think it is also good for health. There is a Greek saying, "Dance is the wedding of movement to music".

d) Azerbaijani people have folk, old, melodious, attractive, lyrical elegant dances, such as **Ay bari bakh**, **Uzun-dara**, **Vaghzali**, **Jeyrani**, etc. Azerbaijan national dances show the characteristic features of the Azerbaijani nation.

**genuine - actual, authentic, ideal*

Figure 13: English Textbook Page 114.

In 7th grade textbook, cultural and intercultural elements were researched, but it was so difficult to find exercises about phrases, sayings, idioms, they are not taught through culture.

The last book also was written by Giztamam Guliyeva and Khalida Rustamova. There are not so many cultural elements, it is difficult to find any proverbs, sayings, idioms, even there are not. All exercises are given for teaching grammar. Most cultural elements are written about Azerbaijan's culture.

On page 24, there is a unit about "Communication". Dada Gorgud's name is mentioned in this text. Dada Gorgud is the most important proof that the Azerbaijani Turk nation has lived on its lands since ancient times. The exact meaning of his name is uncertain, since it can mean "father's father (grandfather)", but can also refer to a "saggar". The language of "Dada Gorgud" is our native language.

Students should know about their values, books. It is good that the information is given about "Dada Gorgud". Idioms, phrases are not taught through culture.

UNIT 2
COMMUNICATION

Lesson 1. The History of Communication

Key words:

exhaustion (n) – tiredness
fire (n) – the flame, light, heat
holy (adj) – sacred, divine, blessed
marathon (n) – a long running race of about 42 km or 26 miles
mediator (n) – peacemaker, negotiator, moderator
miracle (n) – a wonder
swallow (n) – a small bird with long pointed wings

What you'll learn:

- About different means of communication
- The effectiveness of communication
- How people benefit from communicating with each other
- How people sent messages in the past

[k] miracle [θ] marathon

1 GW. Look at the quote, discuss it and answer the questions.

Where there is collaboration, there is cooperation, communication and friendship!

- Can a **fire** be a means of communication? How?
- Can a **swallow** or a **dove** be a means of communication? How?
- Can rocks be a means of communication? How?

INTERESTING TO KNOW!

From ancient times, fire has been *a means of communication**. Even at Dede Gorgud's time on happy days people set a fire at the top of the highest mountain. If there was set one fire, it meant that people celebrated a very special, happy event, if there were set two fires it meant that something wrong had happened, they were in danger or the enemy was at the door.

A dove has always been the symbol of peace all over the world. In old times a dove was as *a mediator* to deliver a message from one place to the other. People communicated with each other by the help of the dove.

When people didn't have the alphabet or they couldn't read or write they drew pictures on the walls or rocks. These pictures tell people the stories of their everyday life, battles and culture. Gobustan is a lively sample and one of the first *holy* places of art, culture of the world where the ancient dance and musical culture are formed.

Figure 14: English Textbook Page 39.

There is a text about "Animals" on page 39. As mentioned, Americans love pets. It is also a part of the culture. Not all countries keep animals at home, some people like animals, some of them afraid of them.

There are several interesting facts, phrases, and sayings about animals. Exercise 6 requires to find the meanings of verbs and phrases. There are four sayings about dogs, so it is good that phrases and sayings are taught through culture.

We can find information about ceremonies/events on page 47. Keywords are given. On this page, there are not any exercises about the text.

Every civilian should know about their past. 20th January is National Mourning Day of Shahids. On page 49 information is given about 20th January. The importance of this day, the meaning of "martyr", the meaning of flowers are taught.

4 IW. Read the Fact File and search for other flowers. Write their usefulness in the life of people.

Our Martyrs are our proud!

FACT FILE

January 20th is known as Black January, in the history of Azerbaijan - the Day of Shehids. In 1990 Soviet troops entered the city of Baku and killed more than one hundred *civilians**. It is celebrated as the *rebirth* of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is also the day of Remembrance of the *victims* of the Nagorno-Karabakh War in 1988. Every January we go to Martyrs' Avenue and put different flowers, especially carnations on their graves.

A martyr – is a person who sacrificed himself for the sake of his motherland.

5 GW. Fill in the chart according to the flowers.

Flowers	Months	Colours	Features	Other
:	:	:	:	:

to look

- for
- like
- at
- up
- through
- after

is the only flower that never appears anywhere as a wild flower/plant. You **have to** plant it.

- Nuray **looks** happy.
- **Look at** these wonderful flowers!
- I'm **looking for** fresh flowers.
- **Look after** the flowers!
- Poppy **looks like** a cup.
- **Look through** the newspapers!
- You should **look up** the flower words in the encyclopedia.
- I love my granny very much and **look after** her.

6 IW. Choose the suitable one and translate the sentences.

- Why do you *look/look up/look at* so tired?
- Aysel *looks/looks through/looks like* her mother.
- I've lost my watch and now I'm *looking at/looking up/looking for* it.
- The primroses *look/look like/look after* stars.
- Shaig *looked at/looked like/looked up* an elegant film director.
- Sebuhi *looks like/looks after/looks for* a rugby player. He's enormous.
- She *is looking at/looking up/looking through* the newspaper now. She's going

Figure 15: English Textbook Page 47.

Phrasal verb “to look” is given and there are several examples about “to look”.

Azerbaijan has national objects, richest ornamental elements, handicrafts, decorative applied arts. Students should learn about national values, meanings of those objects.

It is also important for students to know famous artists to develop their worldview. On page 54 there is information about two famous painters. One of them is from Azerbaijan and the other one is a Spanish painter.

About Azerbaijan's famous painter Sattar Bahlulzadeh (1909-1974) is given on page 54. What type of colors had he use, what is “The Wish of the Land”, what is his inspiration etc.

The second one is about famous Spanish painter Pablo Picasso (1881-1973). His methods, works are mentioned.

We can find several expressions that are required to find their meaning. Exercise is only about them.

As we know films are also included in culture. Every country has its films. The films shaping our beliefs and values, for example, people copy fashion trends from movie stars and musicians. It is also common these days to find societies using figures of speech that are inspired by the film industry.

There is a unit about “My favorite film star” that gives information about Azerbaijan’s national films on page 106.”The Gypsy Girl” and “The Mystery of a Tower” is Azerbaijan’s national films. The film “Gypsy Girl” and “The Mystery of a Tower” are described with new words. Keywords are given at the beginning of the unit.

UNIT 7

FAME

Lesson 1.

My Favourite Film Star

Key words:

capture (v) – occupy, invade, conquer, catch
endow (v) – give as a gift, contribute
evil (adj/n) – damn, badness, devil, harm, injury
hardship (n) – deprivation, difficulty, distress, suffering, trouble
merciless (adj) – pitiless, severe, cruel, heartless
poison (n) – toxin, substance causing death
prevent (v) – stop sb from doing sth
ruler (n) – a person who rules or governs
torture (v) – cause extreme pain to sb, as a punishment

What you'll learn:

- What's the role of the children's films in our life
- Who are famous film stars
- What's the connection between films and the real life
- How films affect people

[tʃə] capture/torture
[z] poison/reason

1 CW. Look, find out what films these pictures are from and say which proverbs refer to them. Give comments on them.

- Knowledge is power!
- A hero dies, his fame remains!
- A friend in need is a friend indeed!
- You know a man by his friends!

- One man, no man!
- Unity is strength!
- Truth will conquer!
- After rain comes fair weather!

2 GW/PW. Fill in the gaps using the key words and expressions. Discuss these questions as well

Figure 16: English Textbook Page 47.

Proverbs are taught through teaching films. Eight proverbs are given as an exercise. Students should look and find out what films those pictures are from and say which proverbs refer to them and

they should give their comments. Some of the films are Azerbaijan's national films and some of them are different countries' films.

If students do not have any information about their national films, it is a good opportunity to learn, because probably they watch films, they get information then do the exercises.

There is also information about movies on page 113. New words are given. Students should research actors and write about their ages, where are they from, their roles, the name of the films on page 114. As a grammar, conjunctions are taught through teaching culture.

2 PW. Read the dialogue and perform it.

Aygul: Have you ever seen "Arshin Mal Alan"?

Ismayil: No. I'm not sure.

Aygul: Haven't you ever heard of it yet? "Arshin Mal Alan" was composed by Uzeyir Hajibayli, the outstanding Azerbaijani composer and playwright, the founder of national professional music and national opera.

Ismayil: And what is the moral of this film?

Aygul: To love, to be loved and create a happy family are seen as the desire in this film. The hero of this film is *merchant* Asgar. Asgar *disguises* himself as an arshinmalchi (*the one who is busy with buying and a selling goods*) as his close friend Suleyman advises him and starts to visit homes selling cloth, *drapery, shawls* to girls and women. Asgar finds his love, Gulchohra in one of the *courtyards* and decides to marry her.

Ismayil: Oh, how interesting!

3 PW. Interview your partner and complete the chart.

Name				
Age				
From				
Lives in				
Job/occupation				
Roles/Parts				
Films				

4 IW. Complete the sentences using the conjunctions:
who, which, that, whom, whose, etc.

- Uzeyir Hajibeyli is the great playwright, composer and musician ... made the world famous film "Arshin Mal Alan".
- Golden Gate is the most famous bridge ... was built in San Francisco.
- Walt Disney was the great cartoonist ... produced a series of classics.
- A dictionary is the book ... gives people the meaning and the translation of the words.
- Jeyhun, ... plays Ismayil in the Azerbaijani film "The Stepmother" really performed an unforgettable role.
- Charlie Chaplin was an actor ...

Figure 17: English Textbook Page 139.

Every nationality has its greetings."Like most cultures in the world, Azerbaijanis like warm and friendly greetings. Men greet each other with a handshake, a kiss on both cheeks, and "salam" (hello).

Official greeting in Azerbaijan is a meeting when Presidents, officials leaders shake hands to greet each other”

All this information is given on page 139, it is only about Azerbaijan’s greetings, but on page 141, there is interesting information about different countries that what are the meanings of greetings and body languages.

- The bow is a mark of respect and greeting in Japan
- Crossing your fingers means good luck in England
- Raising your thumb shows that everything is OK or you are lucky
- Raising your hat is a sign of greeting in Europe
- Taking off a cap was a sign of respect in our country in old times

Lesson 2. “When in Rome Do as the Romans Do!”

Key words:

authority (n) – officials, government, administration
 embrace (v) – give a hug, squeeze
 handicapped (adj/n) – disabled, invalid
 illustrated (adj) – pictorial, containing pictures or other graphical material
 initiate (v) – begin, start, create, establish, set up
 reserved (adj) – unsociable, uncommunicative
 subway (n) – an underground (rail system), metro, tube
 unemotional (adj) – not having or showing strong feelings
 utmost (adj) – greatest, most extreme

What you’ll learn:

- The meaning of: “When in Rome do as the Romans do!”
- The rules about greeting people in our country
- How people greet each other in different countries

[n] accordingly
 [θ] authority/thermal

1 CW. Look and write about each nationality’s greetings.

Sample: Like most cultures in the world, Azerbaijanis like warm and friendly greetings. Men greet each other with a handshake, a kiss on both the cheeks and “salaam” (literally “peace” but meaning “hello”). Official greeting in Azerbaijan is a meeting when Presidents, official leaders shake hands to greet each other.

2 GW. Discuss the questions giving your comments and fill in the KWL table.

* Do you agree with the saying “When in Rome do as the Romans do!”? ... different countries?

Figure 18: English Textbook Page 25.

The students are given exercises like research to find different information or facts about greetings in different countries. I think it is a good way that, if students research by themselves, it can be interesting for them and they can learn more.

In this book, there were also cultural and intercultural elements, grammar, proverbs, sayings, phrases are taught.

7 PW. Correct the wrong sentences giving comments.

1. The Japanese like to work while eating.
2. Seniority is very important for the Americans.
3. The Americans bow the head as a mark of respect.
4. The French like to discuss first, then to have dinner.
5. The British like to talk on/about business before dinner.
6. The bow is a mark of respect and greeting in Azerbaijan.
7. The French have the strictest rules of social and business behavior.

INTERESTING TO KNOW!

1. The bow is a mark of respect and greeting in Japan.
2. Crossing your fingers means good luck in England.
3. Raising your thumb shows that everything is OK or you are lucky.
4. Raising your hat is a sign of greeting in Europe.
5. Taking off a cap was a sign of respect in our country in old times.

8 PW. Ask questions for the answers and act it out.

Shahin: _____ ?

Bella: Oh, yes of course. I've been to Azerbaijan lately and Azerbaijani people traditionally treat any guest with the *utmost* respect. When you are invited into an Azerbaijani home, you'll enjoy everything.

Shahin: _____ ?

Bella: The Azerbaijani host will make sure to make you feel at home, so don't take advantage of their kindness.

Shahin: _____ ?

Bella: Azerbaijanis respect elderly people, so in a bus, tram, *subway* young (er) people always offer children, older people a place to sit.

Shahin: _____ ?

Bella: It is respectful to bend slightly (not a complete bow) when greeting someone older or in a position of *authority*.

Shahin: _____ ?

Bella: Oh, great! Yes, how hospitable and respectful the Azerbaijanis are! And I've told all my friends and relatives about the Azerbaijani people, their customs and traditions, their warm hospitality and care.

9 IW. Search and download more information/facts about greetings in different countries and write a paragraph.

Figure 19: English Textbook Page 115.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, each student should first know their own culture and then know different countries. Each country has its own culture and it should be taught in ELT textbooks. Through culture grammar, idioms, sayings, idioms, phrases can be taught. According to my research, grammar is taught through culture, but in three textbooks, there are not enough idioms, proverbs, sayings. Not only through culture, but also with different ways it should be taught. In my opinion, students should learn them besides grammar, and it is not difficult to teach them, but in general, our culture and different cultures are taught, and if there are not proverbs, sayings, phrases, idioms, teachers can find by themselves and teach.

It should also be taken into account that even though textbooks are the main material in the classroom, textbooks or textbooks alone may not be sufficient for visual presentation and recognition of cultural issues as the best opportunity to get to know a culture. and, accordingly, gaining experience makes it possible to experience them on the spot.

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DECLARATION OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author do not have any interest-based relationship.

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All stages related to this research and research were carried out by the author.